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REPORT ON SEQUENCING OF SAMPLES USING RSE AND NGS (MEME WP3-T3)

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This activity was conducted as part of the task T3 in work package WP3 in **MEME (Multi-centre study on *Echinococcus multilocularis* and *Echinococcus granulosus* s.l. in Europe**: development and harmonisation of diagnostic methods in the food chain), a Joint Research Project under One Health EJP.

1. Aim

Description of the task: To employ a novel approach for *Echinococcus* spp. detection and characterisation by combining DNA-enrichment methods, using parasite-specific DNA-capture probes and magnets, from complex biological samples (e.g. faeces or raw vegetables), and characterisation of captured DNA-fragments using high throughput sequencing technologies (long-read sequencing (Oxford Nanopore Technologies) and short-read sequencing (ILLUMINA)).

In other words this task focus on target captured templates, such as via MC-DNA and/or Region Specific Extraction (RSE) methods (MEME task WP3-T3), and attempt to sequence these using long-read sequencing (ST1) or via Illumina short-read Next Generation Sequencing (ST2) for the identification of *Echinococcus multilocularis* (Em) and *E. granulosus* s.l. (Eg) in complex samples. Because templates prepared from MC-DNA would already had undergone specific regional extraction we also wanted to include these, due to the application of the method for confirmatory purposes for those labs using this method for surveillance. Although one can argue that the RSE-method reported by Dapprich (2016) are now acknowledged a very specific protocol, a wider understanding of 'region specific extraction' have been used in this task. Because there are some limitations to the commercialisation of this kit is still quite early, only few alternatives exists, making it expensive and hard to come by. Therefore, specifically for WP3-T3 ST1, as we already employed an MC-DNA approach for *Echinococcus multilocularis* detection, we wanted to investigate if we could enable characterization by combining the MC-DNA method used in our surveillance and investigate if it was possible to do high throughput sequencing technologies Oxford Nanopore sequencing (nanoporetech.com) (ONT), but for the testing of Illumina NGS (www.illumina.com) the Dapprich RSE method was possible to test.

2. Background and principle of the methods

Detection and sequence characterization of Em and Eg from complex samples (faeces) can be useful for epidemiological studies of prevalence in definitive hosts. For increased sensitivity, magnetic capture based extraction methods (MC-DNA) have been shown to allow very high sensitivity and allow larger volumes of samples to be processed for molecular analysis (Isaksson et al 2014; Øines et al. 2014). Magnetic capturing of molecular targets captured in complex samples can be useful approach to remove contaminants and genetic material of no interest, in complex matrixes such as faeces. Testing the samples with sensitive qPCR methods can be a useful combination for surveillance methods, when screening for low-abundant targets. The magnetic capture DNA extraction and realtime PCR methods from (Isaksson 2014, Øines et al. 2014) is routinely used for the surveillance of *E. multilocularis* by MeME partners. Having a sequencing approach for templates prepared from this protocol would be useful for further identification and risk management of any positive samples, should they be discovered.

Figure 1. Illustration depicting the principle of Magnetic Capture (fishing) DNA extraction protocol for use of *Echinococcus multilocularis* detection in fox faeces. Figure created with Biorender.com.

The annual surveillance programme for EM in Norway performed by the National Veterinary

Institute (Hannes et al. 2021), employ the manual MC-DNA isolation procedure with subsequent qPCR detection (figure 1), for screening of fox faeces. This sensitive extraction method selective target parasite mtDNA in a complex matrix and is capable of detecting very low amounts of parasite material, as even single eggs in large fecal samples may be detected (Øines et al. 2014). Target enrichment of specific extraction of low-abundant targets via a Magnetic Capture based technology, allow more biomass to be processed per sample and low abundant targets to be identified via molecular tools, compared with traditional DNA-protocols where typically only a fraction of the same input material can be processed. There are different concepts that can allow for selective target enrichment and the MC-DNA methodology used in the surveillance methods for *Echinococcus multilocularis*, represent one method where probes used in solution allow the selective pull-out of the targets. But methods rely on only one specific DNA-probe for extraction could limit what regions that can be extracted. There are additional technologies which provide target capture and specific extraction from complex samples. The term Region Specific Extraction (RSE) is a concept introduced by Dapprich et al (2016), and can be an alternative for using specific probes. This concept can be useful on samples The concept of specific extraction of specific target genes often rely on a biotin-streptavidin, where the interaction between a biotin attached to a primer allow after hybridization with the target, and after paramagnetic particles where streptavidin coats the surface

Parasites that can be undetectable after being subjected to traditional nucleic acid isolation approaches in complex samples such as faeces, may be detected, not only due to the great ability of the method to remove contaminants and non-target DNA, but also due to the fact that material can be selectively processed out of a sample. There are many terms describing this approach, Magnetic Capture DNA methods, pull-down assays and recently a new term for this approach combined with nanopore sequencing was described as *TELSeq*, Targeted Enrichment with Long read Sequencing (Slizovskiy et al 2022). The authors found that this was a superior approach superior for the sequencing of low abundant resistance genes in microbiome samples to non-enriched PacBio and short-read Illumina sequencing (Slizovskiy et al 2022).

When using MC-DNA, we know that due to its increased sensitivity, we can expect some samples positive for the MC-DNA/qPCR protocol to only contain very low levels of parasite DNA, especially in the case where only very few eggs are available, and although detected using qPCR-methods, we did not know if these samples could be characterized using this new NGS technology. This task was then initiated to allow testing of material containing DNA from *Echinococcus* samples and investigate if it was possible to employ NGS protocols for the detection and sequence identification of parasite samples prepared from magnetic capture/RSE extraction methods. This task focused to investigate if two different NGS platforms (both long-read/nanopore and short-read/Illumina technology) could be used to identification and characterize samples containing *Echinococcus* spp. in complex (fecal) samples, that was prepared with RSE/MC-DNA methods.

2.1.1 Sub Task 1 Nanopore sequencing of MC target templates

Nanopore sequencing is one of the most recently developed sequence technologies, and is often referred to as one of the most common used long-read sequence technologies, significantly generating longer sequence reads compared with other NGS platforms. Longer reads may facilitate *de-novo* investigations of pathogens, and characterisation of repetitive regions. This technology can be cost-effective, and provide alternatives which practically no capital investment costs. But historically the reads produced by this technology have contained a large proportion of errors, demanding larger dataset when assigning high accuracy consensus sequences. Recent developments in the technology and the chemistry being used, have greatly increased raw read accuracy for this platform, and is now reported to be >99% for some protocols (<https://nanoporetech.com/accuracy>). Being a relatively new technology, the iteration of flow-cells, sequence kit, as well as data analysis tools, is high, and the combinations of kit selection and available protocols have dramatically increased during the couple of years. Compatibility between different kits and flow-cells is important, and rapid platform development may not always provide well- tested suitable protocols, which can also be challenging for users of the technology. Also for research fields outside the main-stream science activities, may need further validations and optimisations.

The nanopore sequence platform, can target high concentrated, or low concentrated

samples, with a variety of different sequence kits. There is a choice of PCR-free kits, which native DNA (or RNA) can be sequenced directly with no need for PCR amplification of the template; The two main options for this are the ligation sequence based kits or the rapid kits. The ligation based kits rely on a ligase enzyme to add some adapter to the ends of DNA-templates which are present in the sample. This protocol can be quite labour and time intensive, so an alternative approach to this can be the rapid sequence kits, where a transposase cleaves the template DNA randomly, and at the same time attaches tags for sequencing on the ends of the cut DNA, where sequence adapters are added. This approach is faster, but would need a bit more template, when compared to PCR based kits. PCR based kits employ an amplification step, after PCR-adapters are attached to the templates, hence the template can be amplified up via PCR, to allow sufficient concentrations for sequencing. At the time of project planning, we had few/none PCR sequencing options from ONT, so a protocol using a PCR-free sequence kit was prioritised. As it is simpler to use, and faster, a rapid protocol would also help fast diagnosis, hence the Rapid Sequence kits were our focus, when testing the suitability of using Nanopore sequencing on MC-DNA, but recent developments in other kits, would warrant future testing as these may be even more suitable for low target levels. The use of samples derived from region specific extraction of samples where parasite material can be present in low numbers, will therefore push the envelope of these kits and protocols, but we hoped that this still would be possible.

2.1.2 Material

Positive material was available either as regular extracted DNA or as native or spiked fecal samples from fox, of parasite material (eggs, adults or parts of parasites) from various cetodes, available from diagnostic samples or samples used in the annual EURL proficiency tests, or from positive control samples prepared for use in the annual surveillance programme. Procedure for MC-DNA follows that of Øines et al. (2014), and with some alternative material to test proof-of-concept on the sequencing, was prepared using a standard DNA isolation protocol using Qiagen qiamp DNA isolation kit (EURL-PT + diagnostic samples).

Fig 2. Figure of (some of) protocols tested in WP3T3 for identification and characterisation using nanopore sequencing. Comparison of reference material extracted with standard DNA-isolation protocol with that of MC-DNA samples. Figure made with Biorender.com.

2.1.3 Results

The use of the nanopore sequence platform for the identification of EM and EG from positive controls prepared using the existing magnetic capture method (from Isaksson 2014), was run directly on a nanopore flow-cell, but a few initial runs failed to produce any usable sequence data from these nanopore sequence runs. Attempts to overcome this by modification of the RSE protocol and sample preparation steps, were carried out. Modification of the region specific extraction (RSE) protocol involved testing of new fishing

probes and attempts to perform a variation of pre-amplification procedures to the RSE templates before sequencing, and was done either by long PCR-tiling, random or targeted whole genome amplification techniques, where some showed great promise for clean parasite samples prepared via standard DNA-isolation procedures;

Genome amplification approach generated usable dataset for the identification of the EURL-samples that were tested, which included *Echinococcus multilocularis*, *Echinococcus granulosus* and *Taenia saginata* (and was compared with a metabarcoding approach as per task WP4T3). DNA-samples provided from EURL ring trial 2022 (5 uL), then some samples from the RSE DNA extraction, was subjected to whole genome amplification (Repli-G, Qiagen) using an adapted protocol from the TeleVir consortia (EJP-TELEVIR) initially developed for metagenomics nanopore sequencing of DNA-viruses. Because the current RSE-protocol only targets mtDNA, our method was adjusted towards mtDNA amplification by including cestode mtDNA primers. Following amplification of the template, these were prepared with the rapid barcoding kit RBK-004 on a Minion nanopore sequence device (MK1C) using a Minion flowcell (MIN-106D) according to the manufacturers recommendations. Data was first base-called, either during the run using Minknow, or afterwards in Guppy (including de-multiplexing). Assembly of Fastq sequence-reads was done in Geneious Prime using the MiniMap2 assembler. The assembly was done against a reference cestode mtDNA sequence (NC_000928 Em). Although a finished well-proven bioinformatics pipeline was not completed within this task, sequence data was from each sample was assembled against a *E. multilocularis* full length reference mitochondrial sequence (NC_000928) using bioinformatics software suite Geneious, using Minimap2, which resulting in an assembly with the reference sequence that allowed long sequences from the sample to be extracted. Although initial assemblies was possible without further modification of the sequences, but it was found that trimming away the sequence of the ND-fishprobe, greatly improved the assembled data, and after analysing a reference sample used in the EURL proficiency tests, an assembly of 17238 reads of the total 96423 reads of this sample, covering fragments of the mitogenome. If only looking at the regions with cover >10x the following fragments were obtained;

Figure 3

Depicting visually the coverage after assembly in Geneious with the mtDNA reference sequence. Plot Assembly and figure was generated in Geneious (v. 2022.2, by Biomatters). The green regions indicate a graphical representation of the coverage logarithmically, indicating a maximum coverage of 10829x in this assembly.

Table 1

Contig #	Relative position in assembly	Number of bases	Genes in this region	Coverage minimum	Coverage maximum	Median coverage
1	48-158	110	tRNA/intergenic region	10	193	115
2	2026-3265	1239	ND5, COX3	10	10829	2197
3	3817-4387	571	COX3, CYTB	10	372	157
4	5407-5984	578	CYTB, ND4L/ND4		389	149
5	6698-7092	395	ND4	12	1102	551
6	10304-10899	596	tRNA/ND3	10	277	43
7	13235-13375	141	L_rRNA	10	210	130
8	13996-14480	485	L_rRNA/tRNA/s_rRNA	10	24	16

Table 1 indicating key data on the coverage after assembly of ca.98 k reads from a long-read sequencing run of a positive control sample containing *Echinococcus multilocularis* DNA, after WGA pre-treatment, and being included in a sequence run as only one of several (11) barcoded samples with the rapid sequencing kit from Oxford nanopore. This example present the data from the assembly of sequence reads from a EURL proficiency sample (*prepared using a standard DNA Qiamp extraction) and was not prepared via a MC-DNA protocol. Data presented include regions with a coverage of min.10 was set arbitrarily. The 8 most covered regions presented were obtained after assembly with a reference mtDNA sequence from *E. multilocularis* (NC000928). Only fragments >100 bases were included here. In total, these fragments represent ca. 30% of the whole mtDNA from this parasite.

Contained assembled sequence reads varying greatly in coverage, and greatly on the different settings and parameters of the assembly. However by selecting various high covered regions and subject these to BLAST-analysis, allowed identification of these

samples, and this approach was successfully performed as part of WP4-T3 by using previously received proficiency trial samples from EURL, which included DNA from *E. multilocularis* (see results Table 1), *E. granulosus* and *Taenia saginata*.

The regions with the highest coverage was subjected to BLAST search. Length varied with the different samples, but as several BLAST searches was performed on different fragments from each sample (>3) which allowed independent verification of different gene targets and successful identification of the samples using different genetic targets from the assembly and matching them to the best hits from the NCBI database.

Samples which derived from MC-DNA in faecal samples, produced only 10-70 fold less data when compared to the ordinary DNA positive controls (140-236 mb of data) where MC-DNA was not performed. This show that the amount of DNA present in the samples is crucial for the success of nanopore-sequencing. One sample however, which was a positive control for MC-DNA, previously prepared from a single adult worm of *Echinococcus* spp., containing no fecal material, did produce significant amount of data (243 mb) and with a high number of reads (ca 138 k). Nevertheless, the bioinformatic analysis of this samples revealed initially only a contig which largely was only an assembly of sequences representing the area of the fish-probe that was used in the MC-DNA procedure.

Initially a hypothesis was that in order to pull out the whole mtDNA, based on other reports Therefore as a means of overcome this, a modification to the magnetic capture protocol, included design and testing of additional biotinylated capture probes were designed to allow the capture of mtDNA from multiple *Echinococcus* spp, but these attempts did not indicate improvement and assembly included basically only the fishing probe sequences (fig 4)

Figure 4

Figure 4 representing the assembly after sequences were generated from a positive control MC-DNA sample, which was isolated using 4 capture probes (3 new). Sequenced data indicated after assembly that the assembly generated in essence just the capture probe sequences.

Material. One samples containing one adult *Echinococcus* worm, was included in a sample without faecal content, but still this protocol generated similar amount of data when compared to those samples isolated with traditional DNA-isolation. However, when compared to the samples that was positive material spiked with faecal content, this sample was not possible to assemble to the reference mtDNA sequence. This seem to suggest that the faecal content influence the recovered amount of sequence data from a sample (ca. 10-fold). This reduction of sequence data is likely due to chemical inhibition of enzymes used for steps in pre-treatment and library preparation of the templates before subjected to sequencing. However, the sample that did not contain faecal material, but was isolated using MC-DNA still resulted in failure of assembly, although the amount of data was on levels with those that were successful in parasite identification. This may indicate that the problem might be due to the biotin labelled fishing-probe influencing aspects of the protocol, or that

these fishing probes created bioinformatic challenges. However, it was not possible to get to the bottom of this within the time left for this task.

2.2 SubTask 2 Detection of the entire mitogenome of *Echinococcus multilocularis* by Region-Specific Extraction method and Illumina based Next-Generation Sequencing

2.2.1 Intro & material

DNA was extracted and processed from Em worm and cyst material according to the Region-Specific-Extraction (RSE) method (Dapprich et al., 2016). By the NGS-based RSE approach from this study, the mitogenome (~13kb) from Em could be successfully captured and amplified. To validate the success and the accuracy of this protocol, the mitogenome from the same Em isolates were also analysed by the whole genome Illumina-based NGS.

2.2.3 Results

With this RSE method, the entire mitogenome of Em could be extracted. The read depth coverage was sufficient (median coverage per isolate ≥ 122 reads) to detect existing SNPs with a high confidence. The comparison of mitogenomes extracted by RSE data with mitogenome data obtained by direct NGS of the whole DNAs showed that the accuracy of the RSE method is consistent. Processing of ten samples and analysis of their mitogenomes showed that the method is able to detect genetic variations between the samples. The number of SNPs varied between 63 and 70 among the isolates collected in Germany. The results from the present study suggest that both approaches can provide a less costly and less time-consuming alternative for parasite identification and characterisation than conventional methods, especially when compared to classical methods i.e. “PCR plus Sanger sequencing”, for clean parasite samples. This method provides a more precise and flexible possibility for discovery of new typing markers as well as efficient analysis of the micro-diversity within the Em population (Figures 13, 14).

Figure 5. Positions of SNPs in mitogenome, detected in the *E. multilocularis* field samples by the RSE-Illumina NGS method.

Figure 6. The number of detected SNPs in respective Mitogenomes in the filed samples applying RSE-Illumina NGS method.

5. Discussion and conclusion

The results from the present study suggest that both of these approaches worked with regular DNA –samples to varying degree, but there were limitations in fully testing this on fecal samples. The results suggest that both, but in particular the Dappich approach followed by Illumina sequence approach, can provide complete mitogenome data on the parasites in question in a very efficient way, as a less time-consuming alternative for parasite characterisation and identification than conventional methods, especially when compared to classical methods i.e. “PCR+Sanger sequencing”, at least for clean parasite samples. Moreover, there were evidence of challenges on the success of using RSE material for the nanopore-sequencing.

Unfortunately there was not enough time to allow direct comparison across the sequence platforms for both these capturing techniques and for all types of samples (including direct-feces).

The NGS approaches suggest that using this approach, it may allow a more precise and flexible platform for discovery and characterisation of microdiversity within the EM

population, which should be further explored.

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